

THE PROCESSES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INNOVATIVE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article examines the impact of changes occurring in the context of innovative development on the tourism potential, with a focus on issues related to evaluating quality service provision. The mechanisms for assessing tourist activities within the tourism sector are explored. Attention is given to the optimal development of tourism based on the innovative characteristics of various tourism sectors in the context of economic modernization.*

Keywords: *tourism, innovative development, tourism potential, quality service, evaluation processes, tourist activity, assessment mechanism, economic modernization, tourism sectors, optimal tourism development.*

Introduction.

In the context of modernization of the national economy, the prospects for economic development of any country completely depend on effective innovation activities in all areas of the economy. In recent years, in our country and its regions with high tourism potential, special attention has been paid to the development of the tourism sector, and this area is considered a promising industry, as well as one of the main and important areas for increasing employment and income of the population. Taking this into account, a number of measures are being implemented to effectively use the tourism potential of our country and attract foreign tourists to our country.

Based on the study of organizational and economic mechanisms for the development and diversification of innovative activities in world tourism, a number of scientific and practical results have been obtained. In particular, scientific research is aimed at enhancing the competitiveness of tourism in the external and internal markets, increasing the place and role of the industry in the country's economy, organizing safe tourism, identifying and developing existing internal capabilities for making optimal management decisions in the industry are becoming relevant.

Analysis of literature on the topic.

Scientific and methodological foundations and economic aspects of the organization of the tourism industry are based on the innovative features of the tourism industry and theoretical and practical problems of development and improvement of the tourism industry in the context of sustainable development of the economy of our Republic, Novikov V.S. B.Sh.Safarov, M.T.Alimova, Research A.A.Eshtaeva and others.

Research works of the above-mentioned scientists serve as an important basis for determining the strategic directions of development of the tourism industry, adaptation of national tourism products to the world market of tourism services, scientific study of theoretical and practical problems of tourism industry. However, in these studies, such issues as the introduction of innovations in the tourism network have not been sufficiently studied, and accordingly, there is less literature devoted to this problem. The need to solve the above issues served as the basis for choosing the topic of this article.

Research methodology.

The methodology of the article analyzes the importance and role of investments in our national economy, including mechanisms for the development of the tourism industry and the use of its potential, starting with the analysis of scientific and increasingly popular sources. Based on this, the main ideas and results of the article can be considered as a methodological basis for developing guidelines for improving and perfecting the tourism industry, and the author's recommendations - as a theoretical and practical guide to improving the tourism industry, development of the tourism industry based on modern marketing principles and other market instruments.

Analysis and results.

Innovative management is one of the poorly developed parts of the mechanism of organizational and economic management of the national economy, not taking into account the fact that innovative activity is a necessary condition for the country's economic growth and improving the quality of life. In a market economy, innovations allow for the intensive development of the economy, ensure the acceleration of current efforts to master the latest achievements of science and technology, provide consumers with high-quality and reliable products of various types.

The result of the analysis of international experience shows that at present in Uzbekistan there is a process of creating and implementing the activities of the most competent scientific and technical potential of industries that have the ability to quickly create responsible tools for the domestic and international market. As a result, we see the development of the national innovation and investment system and its integration into the world scientific and technical system. This is the basis for ensuring the economic development of our country according to a new innovative model.

In order to activate innovation policy, it is necessary to create conditions that stimulate innovation activity in the regions, and this should, first of all, be reflected in preferential rent for the use of production space for small innovative enterprises, if the income from innovation activity exceeds the established percentage of the enterprise's income, a reduction in the rate of income tax paid to the regional budget, etc. The development of small innovative entrepreneurship should become a top priority not only at the level of the republic, but also at the level of regional government bodies.

Organizational factors of state regulation of innovation activity should ensure that the opinions of all interested parties are taken into account and at the same time create conditions for taking measures to stimulate innovation. One of the main goals of innovation policy is to increase competitiveness and at the same time improve the standard of living of people through the use of effective technologies and innovative mechanisms, continuous improvement of personnel skills, ensuring that goods and products occupy leading positions in the domestic and world markets.

Based on the results of the above analysis, the features of tourism development in Uzbekistan are:

- high potential for tourism development in the country, in particular, the abundance of material, spiritual and cultural monuments and a variety of exotic, extreme and new types of tourism for foreigners;

- the fact that the government pays great attention to and supports the development of the tourism sector, as well as the fact that the tourism potential of private, public and public-private partnerships is rapidly developing in large areas;

- that the climatic conditions in the country are suitable for receiving tourists throughout the year and good opportunities have been created for extreme tourists interested in various climatic conditions;

- high potential for attracting tourists due to the relatively low level of seasonal fluctuations due to climatic conditions;

- that the distribution of tourists by age is relatively optimal, that is, most of them are energetic, inquisitive, mobile and physically and financially capable older tourists and others.

If we draw a conclusion based on the results of the analysis, our country and its regions are considered promising tourism destinations and have a number of unique positive features. In particular, if the growth rates in the next two years show that there are still many untapped opportunities in the sector, then a number of unique features of the tourist flow, especially the distribution by years and ages, as well as the fact that seasonal fluctuations are not too high, the types of tourism developing in our country are resistant to various external and internal negative fluctuations on the basis that they are sustainable.

One of the places that attracts foreigners in Uzbekistan is Shakhrisabz, the historical center of which is included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Many admire the value of the cultural and historical monuments and public property located here.

The attractive sides of Uzbekistan are: firstly, more than 30 percent of its territory is covered by mountains, plains and weathered areas where you can relax and walk; secondly, there are more than 5,000 architectural and archaeological sites on the territory of Uzbekistan, about 2,500 of which are under state protection; thirdly, there are many art objects and museums, and tourists always have enough opportunities to use them. Currently, 110 sites in Tashkent, 120 in Samarkand, 220 in Bukhara and more than 300 in Khiva are on display for international tourists. There is also scope to expand the number of excursion routes by including Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Kokan and the cities of the Fergana Valley as a whole. In particular, the "City of Atlas and Silk" route through the city of Margilan can be considered an invaluable excursion route for tourists. This provides opportunities to improve the financial performance of the tourism system as a result of the development of international tourism.

Investments in the tourism sector have their own distinctive features. First of all, these aspects are the risk of irreversibility, since the tourist flow is very sensitive to unnoticed political and economic risks, and these risks can lead to political and social changes in the state of the country and the tourism market. For this reason, it is advisable to provide additional necessary guarantees from the republican and local authorities when organizing investment processes in this area. However, it is only possible to effectively develop tourism and unlock the economic potential of regions by coordinating the activities of the state, industry and tourism structures and aligning their mutual interests.

Nowadays the role of the state in investment processes is, on the one hand, in the centralized (budget funds of different levels) and decentralized (fixed assets of state enterprises and private property) implementation of state investment policy, on the other hand, investment processes are influenced by economic policy (credit, depreciation charges, customs, etc.), carried

out on the basis of other regulatory acts. In these processes, the state investment policy should be focused on stimulating investment growth.

Summary and suggestions.

In short, innovations are one of the most effective factors leading to economic development. As a result of the study of organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of the tourism sector and the introduction of innovations, the need to use digitalization technologies in the tourism sector, advertising new tourism destinations to attract the world's population is substantiated, and this recommendation is being implemented in the practice of the tourism sector.

Based on the information presented in the article, the following suggestions can be made:

- it is necessary to modernize hotel services provided to tourists, pay attention to their quality level;
- establishing the provision of vehicles for temporary use (rent) to tourists from abroad;
- construction of accommodation facilities such as hotels, hostels, motels on intercity routes;
- advertising of electronic albums, presentations and video images about goods and services using innovative digital technologies;
- establishing the use of modern high-speed Internet networks in all regions of the Republic;
- improving the qualifications of hotel and tourism personnel in order to provide quality service;
- installation of terminals and ATMs for cash withdrawals using VISA cards in all areas, including rural and mountainous areas, in order to facilitate purchases using VISA cards in places where tourists travel intensively.

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